

The Clinical Significance of Transcription Factor SOX11, Cell-Cell Adhesion Protein E-cadherin and Zinc Finger Protein BCL11A in Diagnosis of Breast Cancer

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: August 09, 2024</p> <p>Accepted: November 08, 2024</p> <p>Keywords : Adhesion proteins; E-cadherin; BCL11A; SOX11; Proto-oncogene; TNBC; Transcription factors.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14056806</p>	<p><i>Transcription factors (TFs) as sex-determining region Y-box (SOX11) and B cell lymphoma/leukemia 11A (BCL11A) role in breast cancer (BC) and their effect on E-cadherin as a metastasis suppressor or as an invasiveness indicator, are 2 questions to be addressed. We measured by ELISA the serum levels of SOX11, E-cadherin, BCL11A, CEA, and CA15.3 in 45 females with BC, 20 benign tumor cases, and 19 control females. The association of the studied markers with the TNM characteristics in the BC group and the correlations between them and (CA15.3 and CEA) were studied.</i></p> <p><i>Significant elevation in E-cadherin serum levels in cancerous subjects, with a decrease in SOX11 and BCL11A serum levels ($p < 0.05$) in the same group. Serum SOX11 has an excellent AUC either solely or combined with CA15.3. E-cadherin levels can aid as a diagnostic marker in breast carcinomas. Earlier stages in BC were associated with an increase in SOX11 serum levels.</i></p>

Introduction

Breast cancer (BC) is the most frequently diagnosed cancer among women worldwide (1). The magnitude of Egypt's BC burden was unknown until the Egypt National Cancer Registry Program collected and published its results in 2014 (2, 3). According to Egypt's National Cancer Institute (NCI), Egypt registry data for female BC is ranked the first among tumors and invasive-ductal carcinoma (IDC) is the most frequent pathological subtype (4).

BC has many target biomarker approaches to its treatment. However, it is a heterogeneous disease with many different outcomes, instigating discovering new markers; for the sake of better outcome in diagnosis. During the pathogenesis of human cancer, the transcription factors (TF) are commonly deregulated that might cause loss or gain of their function (5). Interest for targeting TFs is now gaining researchers' attention; since they can be highly effective in diagnosis particular malignancies specially cancers related to hormone receptors (6).

The Sex-determining region Y-box (SOX) family is one of the TF families involved in cell differentiation, initiation, and activation of genes (5, 7). Researchers have implicated SOX factors in many aspects of development, including organ development, embryogenesis, sex determination, neurogenesis, and hematopoiesis (7, 8, 9, 10, 11).

SOX family has many diverse and contradictory roles especially in oncology they play a role during cell proliferation, migration, invasion, tumor metastasis, and suppression (12, 13, 14). Possible roles for SOX11 are not fully investigated yet. Moreover, SOX11 serum levels haven't been correlated with the BC disease outcome. Previously, researchers have found that higher cytoplasmic and nuclear *SOX11* expressions are associated with low tumor size, absence of node metastasis, and earlier stages of the disease, as well as prolonged overall survival than those with low expression (15). SOX11 role in tumor growth regulation is highly suggested after addressing a strong nuclear expression of *SOX11* in the ovarian cancer and its correlation with prolonged recurrence-free survival (16).

The *B-cell chronic lymphocytic leukemia (CLL)/lymphoma 11 (BCL11)* gene family members, including the *BCL11A* and *BCL11B* genes are known to be involved in Hodgkin's and non-Hodgkin's B-cell lymphoma (17, 18). They are zinc finger proteins and transcriptional repressors normally expressed from myeloid precursor cells and encodes cysteine two and histidine two (C2H2) gene (19, 20).

BCL11A's precise role in BC is still unclear. However, researchers have found that its level is overexpressed in triple-negative BC (TNBC) more than the other types of BC, and knocking down of *BCL11A* gene is found to decrease the tumorigenicity of TNBC, produce tumors with significantly reduced

sizes and decrease the clonogenic capacity of different TNBC cell lines (21). Interestingly zinc fingers are suggested to be controlled and regulated by SOX TFs (22).

The zinc family protein members are characterized by flanking zinc finger groups, enabling them to bind with a specific DNA binding ability and effectively reducing E-cadherin expression levels (23). BCL11A might affect E-cadherin's level and might not and this is being investigated in this study. E-cadherin is a membrane adhesion protein that plays a crucial role in cancer progression and it might be repressed by some zinc finger proteins family members which encodes cysteine two and histidine two (C2H2) gene (23).

The repression of *E-cadherin* and restraining its functions causes the cell-to-cell adhesion and cell integrity to fade gradually (24). E-cadherin is responsible for cell-to-cell adhesion between epithelial cells, resulting in cell layering as well as regulating cell morphogenesis (25). When cell integrity fades leakage of E-cadherin protein occurs from the cell membrane and its serum level increases. This aids in the invasion and metastasis process of BC, which strongly correlates with tumor aggressiveness and epithelial mesenchymal transition (EMT) to take place (26). This allows E-cadherin to be considered a tumor suppressor protein against cell metastasis and cancer aggressiveness (25).

In the current study, we are focusing on measuring the serum level of the transcription regulator SOX11 and assessing its correlation to the proto-oncogene BCL11A and cell-to-cell adhesion protein marker E-cadherin. We are also studying if they are related to various malignant BC types or stages and furthermore, to the pathological characterizations (TNM). The possibility that the studied TFs would affect the E-cadherin levels is also investigated. This study is conducted in an attempt to identify new molecular markers representing the future perspective for substituting the classical non-specific markers of the past, with the more efficient marker(s) related to earlier stages diagnosis or better outcome.

Subjects, Materials, and Methods:

The study groups were recruited from the NCI (Egypt), Cairo University. Pretreated patients recently diagnosed with BC or benign cases, participated in the study.

Ethics Statement: The ethical committees at the Faculty of Pharmacy, Ain Shams University approved, and the NCI (Egypt), Cairo University approved the study protocol (code number IRB00004025). The study was carried out under the regulations and recommendations of the Declaration of Helsinki (WMA 2013). Written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Inclusion criteria

Women included in the malignant group were (45 cases) 39 diagnosed with IDC and 6 cases with Invasive Lobular Carcinoma (ILC) before any treatment. Their average age was 47 (ranging from 30 to 69). Benign group cases included 20 women, diagnosed with fibrocystic changes or fibroadenoma tumors and their average age was 34 (ranging from 25 to 48).

The study subjects underwent a physical examination. Detailed medical history and demographic data was recorded.

Exclusion criteria

Included males and females of age less than 25 or more than 70, subjects receiving any chemotherapy or radiotherapy, patients with blood disorder diseases, any cancer other than BC. Additionally, patients with incomplete data or histopathology diagnosis and patients with distant metastasis were excluded.

Control group

For the control group, 19 women were recruited. Their average age was 42 years (ranging from 30 to 60 years).

Participants data

Clinical data were obtained from medical records and the original pathology reports. These data were compiled in an Excel sheet.

The following data parameters were recorded and assessed: age of the patient, tumor size (defined by mammography or magnetic resonance techniques diameter (mm or cm) on diagnosis), initial tumor stage, and nodal status according to the TNM classification of the American Joint Committee on Cancer (AJCC) guidelines.

All histopathological parameters and tumor subtypes data included in the study were assessed by the pathologists and were derived from the original pathology reports found in the NCI. Breast Imaging-Reporting and Data System (BIRADS) classification was performed according to the American College of Radiology guidelines. Specialized pathologists performed scoring at the Cairo University and NCI Pathology Department. These scorings were made according to standardized protocols and the pathologist was unaware of the study objective.

Blood samples collection and preparation

Peripheral blood samples were withdrawn from the patients at the end of the clinical examination interview. The blood samples were divided into two aliquots, the routine work analyses were measured in the same day of the blood collection and the remaining samples were kept at -80 °C till time of ELISA assays by the microplate reader (Sunrise, Tecan, Switzerland).

Biochemical analysis

Liver enzymes and kidney function tests (Spectrum, Hannover, Germany), were determined by spectrophotometric measurements. ELISA was used to determine serum levels of SOX11, E-cadherin, and BCL11A (Glory Science Co., Ltd, China). These serum level tests were conducted in addition to CA15.3 and CEA (DRG, Germany), according to the manufacturers' instructions.

Statistical analysis

We conducted all statistical analyses using the SPSS statistical package for Windows Version 23.0 (SPSS Software, Chicago, IL, USA). The data's normal distribution was analyzed; continuous variables were expressed mean \pm (SEM) using the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) test. The median (interquartile range) for nonparametric data using the Mann-Whitney *U* test and Kruskal-Wallis *H* test was also used. The best cut-off values were calculated from the area under the ROC curve (AUC) for the investigated parameter(s) (SOX11, E-cadherin, and BCL11A). Correlations were assessed using the Spearman correlation coefficient (*r*) and *p*-values < 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

Results:

Clinical and biological analysis of the study populations for control, benign and malignant groups

Anthropometric measurements, BIRADS, liver enzymes, and kidney functions were recorded. CA15.3 and CEA as well as the studied parameters (SOX11, E-cadherin, and BCL11A), showed a significant difference among control, benign, and malignant groups (Table 1). There was a significant median difference in SOX11 levels between malignant (135 pg/ml) and benign (234 pg/ml) groups ($p \leq 0.001$) and between malignant (135 pg/ml) and control groups (257 pg/ml) ($p \leq 0.001$). Moreover, there was a significant median difference in E-cadherin between malignant (4284 pg/ml) and benign group (3880 pg/ml) at $p < 0.05$ and between malignant (4284 pg/ml) and control group (3403 pg/ml) at $p < 0.05$. The significant mean difference in BCL11A between malignant (9583 pg/ml) and control (10820 pg/ml) groups at $p < 0.05$ (Table 1).

The cancerous and non-cancerous groups

Table 2 revealed the SOX11 median level in cancerous (135 pg/ml) and non-cancerous groups (239 pg/ml) with a significant difference between groups. Also, a significant median difference in E-cadherin between cancerous (4284 pg/ml) and non-cancerous groups (3542 pg/ml) ($p < 0.05$) was recorded. There was a significantly mean difference for the proto-oncogene BCL11A between cancerous (9583 pg/ml) and (10463 pg/ml) for non-cancerous groups.

ROC curve for studied parameters

ROC curves were plotted in (Fig.1 - 5) to illustrate the diagnostic capacity of the studied markers, single and combined. The cut-off point for SOX11 (Fig. 1) was set at 162 pg/ml at which we achieved an 84% sensitivity and 87% specificity and $p \leq 0.001$. The AUC was 0.91 and the 95% CI was 0.84 to 0.97. The cut-off point for E-cadherin (Fig. 2) was set at 3973 pg/ml at which we achieved 71 % sensitivity and 79.5% specificity at a $p < 0.05$. The AUC was 0.68 and the 95% CI was 0.56 to 0.8. The best cut-off point for BCL11A (Fig. 3) was set at 9960 pg/ml at which we achieved 42% sensitivity and 38.5% specificity, with an AUC was 0.36 and also 95% CI 0.24 to 0.47.

The cut-off point CA15.3 (Fig. 4) was set at 21 U/ml at which we achieved 80% sensitivity and 79.5% specificity at a $p \leq 0.001$. The AUC was 0.89 and the 95% CI was 0.81 to 0.95. An increase in the AUC of CA15.3 from 0.89 to 0.93 after combining with SOX11 marker (Fig. 5) was observed, in addition to an increase in the sensitivity from 80 % to 91 % and specificity from 79.5 % to 89 %.

Association between the studied parameters and TNM staging among BC patients

It was found that there is a significant difference in median SOX11 serum elevation levels in stage II BC cases in comparison to stage III BC cases at $p < 0.05$ (Table 3). However, no significant difference between different tumors sizes T1-T2 ≤ 5 cm and T3-T4 ≥ 5 cm and node metastasis N0 and \geq N1 for SOX11, E-cadherin, and BCL11A.

Association between the studied parameters, histopathological grades and types of BC among BC cases

For different subtypes of BC, no significant difference in serum level was observed for SOX11 and BCL11A. Among luminal A subtype the median level for E-cadherin was significantly elevated in comparison to the median E-cadherin serum level among the TNBC subtype at $p < 0.05$ (Table 4).

Correlations analysis of the studied parameters

Studying serum correlations between continuous parametric (BCL11A) and non-parametric assays (CEA, CA15.3, SOX11, and E-cadherin) revealed a significant negative correlation between CA15.3 and SOX11 at $p < 0.05$. A significant positive correlation was observed between SOX11 and BCL11A $p < 0.05$ (Table 5).

Discussion:

SOX11 TF is one of the SOXC groups, which is mainly expressed in developing neurons and astrocytes in the human brain (8). Protein levels of SOX11 are found to be expressed in the endocrine tissues, bone marrow tissues, lungs, pancreas, and GIT tract (7, 15, 27, 28, 29).

Measuring SOX11 serum levels in healthy and diseased subjects was one of our aims. However, a previous study showed that normal cells are enriched with silencing histone marks on the *SOX11* promoter, which has a low degree of methylation (30). But malignant cells have a high degree of methylation, inversely

correlating with *SOX11* gene expression levels, proving a diverse pattern in promoter methylation of SOX11 in the cases of solid tumors in comparison to B-lymphomas (30).

SOX11 promoter methylation can proceed (or not) despite protein expression. A study on epithelial ovarian cancer cell lines reveals that highly promoter methylated cells correlates with a complete lack of SOX11 expression at both mRNA and protein levels (27). This is also observed among nasopharyngeal carcinomas (28).

Possibly in breast tumor-genesis, there might be overexpression of *SOX11* gene or up-regulation first, followed by promoter methylation then down-regulation in the gene and protein expression of SOX11. This would explain SOX11 lower serum levels among malignant subjects in comparison to healthy controls. This observation warrants further research on the expression levels of SOX11 and its correlations with other tumor subtypes and the promoter methylation status.

SOX11 serum levels were significant with tumor stages, as higher serum median levels were observed in stage 2 in comparison to stage 3. SOX11 serum levels were also associated with smaller tumor size and the absence of node metastasis. In concordance with the public data; the overexpression of SOX11 correlates with better prognosis in breast, ovarian and gastric cancers (15, 16, 29).

Spearman's correlation significantly showed a negative correlation between SOX11 and CA15.3. This relationship strengthens the suggestion that higher expression of SOX11 is associated with better disease outcome and earlier tumor stages.

SOX11 silencing inhibit apoptosis by inhibiting caspase-9-3-7-PARP signaling and desensitizing mantle cell lymphomas to the anti-cancer drugs (31). Also, knocking down of SOX11 in mantle cell lymphoma cell lines is associated with an increase in tumor growth rate (32). SOX11 silencing decreases cell cycle protein regulators, promoting G1 phase conversion to the S phase (31). All these effects increase tumor aggressiveness and cancer burden.

Tumor suppressor functions of SOX11 is supported by the tumor suppressor functions of SOX families through blocking of Wnt/catenin signaling pathway and the invasion related genes (33).

Human E-cadherin is responsible for cell-to-cell adhesion. Loss in E-cadherin expression is found to be associated with metastasis and lobular carcinomas in comparison to IDC carcinoma (34). Tumor progression is often associated with the loss of E-cadherin function and the transition to a more motile and invasive phenotype. Losing E-cadherin and the resulting suppression or weakening of cell-to-cell adhesion causing protein leakage from the membrane and its rise in serum levels, also losing of E-cadherin gradually contributes to metastasis and initiation of the primary steps in the EMT process (35). EMT is the coordinated destabilization of cell to-cell contacts and the acquisition of a more migratory and invasive mesenchymal phenotype (36).

Regarding the diagnostic utility of serum E-cadherin to differentiate between cancerous from non-cancerous cases, the ROC curve was plotted with an AUC 0.68 which is a fair AUC. Therefore, E-cadherin can be used combined with SOX11 or with conventional markers such as CA15.3 and not being used solely, to improve all-usefulness in BC diagnosis.

Comparing the use of a fixed cut-off value, serum SOX11 has an excellent AUC 0.91. SOX11 can be used to diagnose and differentiate between cancerous and non-cancerous cases. This raises the possibility that this parameter can be used as a strong diagnostic marker either solely or combined with one of the specific markers such as CA15.3. Combining SOX11 with CA15.3 increased the AUC from 0.89 (CA15.3) to 0.93 (combined), sensitivity and specificity of the diagnosis, all these previous values were obtained and showed an improvement of the diagnostic utility than using CA15.3 alone.

By stratifying patients in the malignant group, according to BC subtypes, a significant difference in E-cadherin levels in luminal A and TNBC subtypes was observed. This is suggested to be due to the increase in the levels of BCL11A in the TNBC group. High levels of BCL11A might decrease the intra-cellular expression levels of E-cadherin. BCL11A shares the same gene family of ZEB proteins (C2H2 type) which can hypothetically share a similar mechanism on E-cadherin repression.

In the current study, E-cadherin levels were non-significant when groups were stratified by tumor stages. However, preserved E-cadherin expression in many studies is associated with a better prognosis, while the reduction of E-cadherin expression is associated with a poor prognosis (37, 38, 39).

Likely, E-cadherin has a more diagnostic function in differentiating between cancerous and non-cancerous groups and between metastatic and non-metastatic groups, rather than differentiating between stages of BC. Spearman's correlation showed no serum correlation between E-cadherin and either CEA or CA15.3 serum levels.

The significant serum BCL11A mean levels difference between cancerous and non-cancerous subjects suggests a process of down-regulation to BCL11A during the occurrence process of malignancy. This is despite TNBC breast subtype was associated with higher BCL11A mean levels, than the non-cancerous group. This can justify the aggressiveness of this BC subtype. No significant differences in BCL11A and the histopathological characteristics were observed. Mean BCL11A level was the highest in TNBC and the lowest in Herceptin BC subtype.

SOX11 and BCL11A are both expressed from lymphoid tissues (40, 41). Both are found to regulate the B-cell-specific activator protein (pax5) the protein responsible for the early B-cell differentiation stage (42, 43). The significant positive correlation between SOX11 and BCL11A proteins in blood might suggest a common regulatory pathway of the two proteins (markers) to be explored.

This is also supported by the reactivation of the embryonic developmental programs in mature mammary breast cells with mouse Breast Cancer Gene (BRCA1 -/-) deleted or mutated gene. In these mammary breast cells, SOX11 and BCL11A are activated along with other TFs (44).

Study Limitations: These findings are for pre-treated subjects and may not translate to post-treated subjects. Despite the limited number of subjects enrolled in this study, results can still guide further research directions.

Conclusion:

This study showed a significant elevation variation in E-cadherin serum levels in cancerous subjects. However, there was also a significant decrease in SOX11 and BCL11A serum levels in this BC study group. An increase in serum SOX11 levels was associated with earlier stages of BC. Serum SOX11 has an excellent AUC and can be used either solely or combined with CA15.3 to improve BC diagnosis. E-cadherin can be used combined with SOX11 or with conventional markers such as CA15.3 and not being used solely. BCL11A has no significant role in all BC subtypes. TNBC breast subtype was associated with a higher proto-oncogene BCL11A mean level than the non-cancerous group.

Recommendations and future directions: Study the relation of the promoter methylation status; epigenetic modification and SOX11 expression.

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